

Title

Supplement to Exploring metabolic effects of the long-acting growth-differentiation factor 15 (GDF15) receptor agonist (MBL949) in randomized placebo-controlled trials in healthy subjects with and without obesity

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ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT05199090

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Abstract:

Background: Growth Differentiation Factor 15 (GDF15), a divergent member of the TGF- β superfamily, signals via the hindbrain glial-derived neurotrophic factor receptor alpha-like and rearranged during transfection receptor co-receptor (GFRAL-RET) complex. In nonclinical species, GDF15 is a potent anorexigen leading to substantial weight loss. MBL949 is a half-life extended recombinant human GDF15 dimer.

Methods: MBL949 was evaluated in multiple nonclinical species and then in humans in two randomized and placebo-controlled clinical trials. In the Phase 1 first-in-human, single ascending dose trial MBL949 or placebo was injected subcutaneously to overweight and obese healthy volunteers (n=65) at doses ranging from 0.03 to 20 mg. In Phase 2, MBL949 or placebo was administered subcutaneously every other week for a total of 8 doses to obese participants (n=126) in five different dose regimens predicted to be efficacious based on data from the Phase 1 trial.

Results: In nonclinical species, MBL949 was generally safe and effective with reduced food intake and body weight in mice, rats, dogs, and monkeys. Weight loss was primarily from reduced fat, and metabolic endpoints improved. A single ascending dose study in overweight or obese healthy adults demonstrated mean terminal half-life of 18-22 days, and evidence of weight loss at the higher doses. In the Phase 2, weight loss was minimal following biweekly dosing of MBL949 for 14 weeks. MBL949 was safe and generally tolerated in humans over the dose range tested, adverse events of the gastrointestinal system were the most frequent observed.

Conclusion: The prolonged half-life of MBL949 supports biweekly dosing in patients. MBL949 had an acceptable safety profile. The robust weight loss observed in nonclinical species did not translate to weight loss efficacy in humans.

Trial registration: ClinicalTrials.gov NCT05199090

Funding: Novartis

1 Supplemental Material:

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3 Methods:

4 Rat Studies

5 Male Wistar Han rats (Charles River Laboratories; Wilmington MA, USA) received MBL949 (0.5
6 mg/kg) or vehicle (30 mM sodium acetate, pH 4.0) as a single subcutaneous dose. To
7 determine if rats would display tachyphylaxis to MBL949, a second dose of MBL949 (0.5 mg/kg)
8 or vehicle was administered subcutaneously 14-days after the initial dose. Before and after
9 treatment food intake and body weight were measured, and tail vein blood was collected for
10 MBL949 exposures after each dose.

11 Dog Studies

12 Eight male beagle dogs weighing 9-14 kilograms were fed a chow diet (Hill's J/D diet; Topeka
13 KS, USA). Dogs received a subcutaneous injection of vehicle (50 μ L/kg, 30 mM sodium acetate,
14 pH 4.0), and food intake and body weight were monitored for 3 weeks. Subsequently, half of the
15 animals received a 1 μ g/kg dose of MBL949, while the other half received a 15 μ g/kg dose of
16 MBL949 (both at 50 μ L/kg). Body weight and food intake were measured before and after
17 treatment, and blood was collected to determine MBL949 exposures. During the first 96 hours,
18 the dogs were offered chow *ad libitum*, with a maximum of 500 g offered during any time period.
19 Thereafter, the dogs were fed their normal allotment of 225 grams chow/day.

20 Results

21 MBL949 also reduced food intake and body weight in rats and dogs (**Supplementary Figure 1**).
22 In Wistar Han rats MBL949 (0.5 mg/kg) injected subcutaneously reduced food intake by
23 approximately 50% over the first 3 days and body weight by 10% (or 15% vehicle adjusted) on
24 Day 6 (**Supplementary Figures 1A and B**). When food intake and body weight returned to
25 baseline levels on Day 14, a second dose of MBL949 (0.5 mg/kg) was administered. Similar
26 reductions in food intake and vehicle adjusted weight loss were observed following the second
27 MBL949 injection, consistent with no tachyphylaxis of the response (**Supplementary Figures**
28 **1A and 1B**). MBL949 exposures were similar over the two injections with a circulating half-life of
29 3.5 days (**Supplementary Figure 1C**).

30 Beagle dogs were highly sensitive to MBL949. A single 15 μ g/kg dose of MBL949 reduced food
31 intake by 85% over the first 4 days and body weight by 15% 21 days after MBL949 was injected
32 (**Supplementary Figures 1D and 1E**). The apparent half-life of MBL949 in dogs was
33 approximately 14 days (**Supplementary Figure 1F**).

34 Supplementary Figure Legend

35 **Supplementary Figure 1:** MBL949 reduces food intake and body weight in rats and dogs. Rats
36 received MBL949 (0.5 mg/kg) subcutaneously on day 0 and 14 and daily food intake (A), body
37 weight (B) and plasma MBL949 levels (C) were measured. Dogs received a single
38 subcutaneous dose of MBL949 (either 1 or 15 μ g/kg) and cumulative food intake (D), body
39 weight (E), and plasma MBL949 levels (F) were measured. Data are presented as group means
40 \pm SEM, n = 4 vehicle and 8 MBL949-treated rats and n=4 per group for dogs. Data were

41 analyzed by 2-way ANOVA with a Bonferroni multiple comparisons test. In (A) $P < 0.01$ for the
 42 first 4 days post each MBL949 injection. In (B) $P < 0.01$ for all days except day 14. In (D) for the
 43 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ MBL949 group, $P < 0.05$ versus all groups from 24h onward. In (E) for the 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$
 44 MBL949 group, $P < 0.05$ versus all groups from day 4 onward. Neither rat nor dog GDF15 is
 45 detected by the human GDF15 ELISA, so GDF15 is equivalent to MBL949 concentrations.

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47 **Supplementary Figure 1:**

48 **MBL949 reduces food intake and body weight in rats and dogs**

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